

DESIGNING DYNAMIC TESTS TO ASSESS RATE DEPENDENCE IN LARGE-SCALE CRACK BRIDGING

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SUMMARY

A numerical investigation is used to design test geometries and loading histories that are suitable for probing the mode II bridging effect of through-thickness reinforcement in composite laminates loaded at high strain rates. The bridging effects are represented by a cohesive law and tests are sought that will determine any rate dependence in its parameters. Information content in the dynamic case is addressed by focusing on regimes within the full computed solution space where crack growth is approximately steady state, the crack sliding speed is constant, and the crack profile is at least partially linear. These conditions allow quick insight into the information content of experiments. Results show that hypothetical rate-dependence in the cohesive law causes strong and measurable changes in the regimes of simple behavior, if the tests are properly selected to vary the crack sliding speed. The estimates of information content are conservative, in that analysis of the total solution regime will necessarily contain more information than analysis of the regimes of simple behavior alone.

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